

MODERN PHARMACOTHERAPY OF TREATMENT OF LIVER DISEASES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11098058>

Abstract. *Liver diseases, the symptoms of which are expressed in constant nausea, heartburn, an unpleasant odor from the oral cavity, and a yellowish skin color have become more and more frequently diagnosed in the last decade. Many people know about liver diseases today. The main, most common are cirrhosis, hepatitis, and cholecystitis. Liver treatment will depend on the disease, its stage, and the individual characteristics of the course.*

Keywords: *phosphatidylcholine, fatty liver dystrophy, cholera, hepatitis.*

The main task of the liver is the filtration of foreign, toxic, harmful substances, the work of the organ is directly related to the functionality of the pancreas, duodenum, stomach, and dysfunctions always lead to the appearance of chronic diseases. In addition, there are up to 50 different diseases in medicine that are directly or indirectly related to liver malfunctions: these are nervous and endocrine disorders, edema, circulatory disorders and other manifestations. Therefore, complex action is required from drugs aimed at eliminating the causes of liver diseases. Many complex drugs for the treatment of the gastrointestinal tract and in particular the liver is used to eliminate the effects of toxic effects of substances. The use of drugs is justified and effective after prolonged courses of medication, alcoholism, radiation exposure, accidental poisoning, lesions of the internal organs of the digestive system, chronic diseases, including fibrosis and cirrhosis of the liver. The products are available in various dosage forms, including tablets, herbal preparations, essences and concentrates, oils, etc.

Phosphatidylcholine (phospholipids) is the main active ingredient of preparations of this type of hepatoprotectors, has a lipotropic property: it helps to normalize and improve cholesterol, transport and fat metabolism in the liver. Normalizes protein metabolism, restores lipid metabolism, slows down the loss of enzymes, inhibits the growth of connective tissue, stops the loss of enzymes, active substances

Phospholipid-based drugs are successfully used to treat various severity of liver diseases, including severe viral and toxic lesions, and are also used in therapy to restore body functions - after courses of radiotherapy, radiation pollution.

Diseases in which phospholipids can be prescribed:

- fatty liver dystrophy
- alcoholic and viral hepatitis
- fibrosis and cirrhosis of the liver
- lesions of the gland in diabetes mellitus
- adjunctive therapy for psoriasis
- preparation for liver surgery and recovery after surgery

- radiation sickness
- toxicosis during pregnancy

Vegetable flavonoids. These are natural antioxidants, natural, natural compounds, their mechanism of action is the neutralization of free radicals (particles that affect the cell membrane). The sources of such medicines are herbal ingredients: turmeric, celandine, dymyanka, milk thistle. Like the medicines of the previous group, herbal flavonoid preparations are used for a wide range of liver diseases, they are preferred because of the minimal list of adverse reactions. In addition to the treatment of liver diseases, plant extracts and remedies of natural origin have a multidirectional effect: they are used as antispasmodics, medicines that improve the production and outflow of bile. They are used to treat chronic liver lesions, severe forms of diseases:

- Toxic lesions with cholestasis
- Chronic hepatitis
- Chemo- and radiotherapy (including treatment of neoplasms)
- Alcoholic lesions
- Fatty degeneration and dystrophy
- Consequences of viral hepatitis

Choleretics. Such drugs include drugs of synthetic and herbal origin, and the mechanisms of increasing the volume of bile also differ. There are two types of drugs – true choleretics and hydrocholeretics. True choleretics are a separate subgroup of drugs for restoring liver function, medications increase the formation of bile acids, bile secretion. Medicines that already contain bile acids in each tablet, which are necessary to normalize healthy fluid withdrawal. They are used in the treatment of cholangitis, cholecystitis, and chronic hepatitis. In addition, some types of drugs have a positive effect on the functionality of the gastrointestinal tract, in particular, improve intestinal peristalsis, help eliminate constipation, eliminate flatulence. In addition, ursodeoxycholic acid is an effective immunomodulator used in the treatment of diseases associated with high cholesterol levels. Against the background of a wide range of use of UDCA drugs, their intake is limited: contraindications – acute forms of the disease, obstruction, stages of decompensation, pronounced violations of the functionality of the pancreas, kidneys.

Biologically active additives, herbal components – hepatoprotectors and organotropic agents in combination with other substances play a certain role in the treatment of the gastrointestinal tract, gallbladder and liver. The ingredients in the composition of each such drug have a complex effect on the body:

- membrane stabilizing (restore the integrity of liver cells, their properties, structure)
- antioxidant (protection of cells from destruction by active oxygen)
- immunomodulatory and restorative
- regenerating intestinal microflora
- choleretic
- support with vitamins, proteins and trace elements.

To all those who use homeopathic medicines, manufacturers of this type of products offer a choice of hepatoprotective formulations, including for the treatment of cirrhosis of the liver – in tablets, injection solutions, granules.

The disease is associated with:

- poor nutrition;
- consumption of fatty foods;

the use of narcotic substances;
drinking alcoholic beverages;
hepatitis infection;
sugar sickness;
metabolic disorders;
poor environmental conditions.

The constant use of the same medications plays a negative role. Often, damage to the body can be caused by toxic substances. The genetic background also plays an important role. Autoimmune processes that affect liver cells begin in the body. The cause of the disease can be a banal addiction to diets. Drastic weight loss can lead to cirrhosis.

Liver diseases have certain symptoms and treatments. Liver disease causes acne on the skin. A person constantly experiences a feeling of hunger and thirst, some parts of the skin are affected by itching. There is a drop in vision. A sick person experiences hot and cold flushes. He suffers from insomnia, tachycardia is noted. There is a noticeable thinning of hair and eyebrows, and cramps. Atherosclerotic plaques may appear in the brain, heart, intestines and vascular system of the legs. Chronic diseases include hepatitis, which has several varieties. Difficult-to-treat diseases have a viral etiology. Usually, an individual approach is applied to such patients.

The liver, whose disease and treatment are difficult, should be entrusted to the supervision of an experienced specialist. We employ only qualified specialists. They have extensive knowledge in this field, as well as extensive practice.

Different types of liver diseases significantly worsen the quality of life, and medicines are responsible for restoring the normal functioning of this organ, whose effect extends to the liver itself, as well as to the gallbladder. All drugs for the liver and ensuring its healthy functionality are a large group of hepatotropic drugs. With impaired digestion, pain in the liver, as well as for preventive purposes, taking medications for the liver will help get rid of unpleasant symptoms and stop the development of the disease. Without timely diagnosis and treatment of any of the liver diseases, except for an obvious deterioration in well-being, metabolism, hormone and enzyme production are disrupted, and cholesterol levels rise.

Timely treatment of liver diseases is a task of paramount importance, both for the medical staff of our center and for the patient. Responsible adherence to the doctor's recommendations turns the treatment of liver diseases into a predictable process. Based on the type and course of the process, an experienced doctor offers conservative or surgical treatment for liver disease. It may include vitamin, herbal preparations, intensive infusion therapy, endoscopic or open interventions.

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